

ХРОНІЧНА МІГРЕНЬ ТА ДЕБЮТ РОЗСІЯНОГО СКЛЕРОЗУ В ПАЦІЄНТКИ ПІСЛЯ ПЕРЕНЕСЕНОГО COVID-19: КЛІНІЧНИЙ ВИПАДОК

CHRONIC MIGRAINE AND MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS ONSET IN A PATIENT AFTER COVID-19 INFECTION: A CLINICAL CASE

Гончар А. В.

Honchar A. V.

Універсальна клініка «Оберіг»

м. Київ, Україна

МС "Oberig"

Kyiv, Ukraine

e-mail: honchar.anastasiya@gmail.com

Specificity: The aim of this clinical case is to show a clinical presentation of comorbidity of migraine and multiple sclerosis (MS) in a patient after Covid-19 and to understand the possible role of Covid-19 vaccine in the MS onset.

A 30 y.o. female came to an outpatient clinic in March 2021 with a history of migraine without aura whose frequency had increased up to 20 days/month after Covid-19 infection in October 2020. She was taking escitalopram 20 mg during the last 6 months because of generalized anxiety disorder, also got a botulinum A toxin migraine therapy 3 months before with a positive effect.

Neurological examination on the presentation was normal. Blood tests and non-contrast brain MRI – normal. Anxiety and depression screening scale (HADS) testing revealed A – 12 points(p), D – 5p.

She switched from escitalopram to duloxetine up to 60 mg +pregabalin 75 mg and start regular physical activity.

In summer 2021 the therapy was changed due to lack of efficacy – from duloxetine to topiramate 50 mg in the morning + amitriptyllin 25 mg in the evening + botulinotherapy, which made a significant improvement to the migraine – headache days reduced to 8.

She had her first dose of the Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 vaccine on August 22. On the 1st of September, she got new complaints - periodic numbness and tingling of hands, after that the feeling of unpleasant burning in the right leg developed, which was moving up to the spine and abdomen. The doctor decided to switch from topiramate and add 75 mg of pregabalin. After 2 weeks complaints were almost resolved.

On the 22 of September, she had the second dose of COVID-19 vaccine, and a day after – new complaints: a feeling of electricity passing from the neck to the lower spine while neck flexing. On examination – there was positive Lermitt's sign, hands and feet dysesthesia, + Romberg sign, anisoreflexia S>D on the left knee, other neurological examination was normal.

On brain and cervical spinal cord non-contrast MRI in T2/FLAIR several MS-suspicious lesions were founded: periventricular, subcortical, intramedullar, not enhanced on contrast MRI.

Additional serological tests were negative.

Lumbar puncture revealed type 2 synthesis oligoclonal Ig G.

Thus the patient met the 2017 MacDonalD's criteria for MS, started taking Copaxone 40 mg 3 times a week. She admitted no relapses yet. She has only 2 headache days a month, doesn't take any migraine prophylaxis.

Discussion. It is already known that migraine occurs 2 to 3 times more frequently in patient with MS than in the general population.^{1,2} with overall rates between 21% and 69%.¹

Still, the effects of this association are unclear, with hypotheses suggesting that migraine may be a precursor of MS, that migraine and MS share a common pathophysiology, and that migraine experienced in MS is a distinct subtype³.

Also, remains unclear the possible role of SARS-CoV-2 infection in unveiling definite MS. Described cases in literature with MS onset after COVID-19 might be (a) of purely casual relation, (b) non-specific, (c) specific⁴.

Regarding Covid-19 vaccination and its possible contribution to MS onset - there is only scarce data⁵.

Conclusion. In this case, a patient's migraine significantly worsened after Covid-19, and after the second dose of anti-Covid-19 first episode of MS occurred.

Large case-control studies are needed to test a possible association between SARS-CoV-2 infection and MS development as well as an association between migraine and MS, between Covid-19 vaccination and MS onset.

References:

1. Kister I, Caminero AB, Monteith TS, et al. Migraine is comorbid with multiple sclerosis and associated with a more symptomatic MS course. *J Headache Pain.* 2010;11:417-425.
2. Applebee A. The clinical overlap of multiple sclerosis and headache. *Headache.* 2012;52:111-116.
3. Kister I, Munger KL, Herbert J, Ascherio A. Increased risk of multiple sclerosis among women with migraine in the Nurses' Health Study II. *Mult Scler.* 2012;18:90-97.
4. Sarwar S, Rogers S, Mohamed A S, et al. (October 25, 2021) Multiple Sclerosis Following SARS-CoV-2 Infection: A Case Report and Literature Review. *Cureus* 13(10): e19036. doi:10.7759/cureus.19036
5. Nistri R, Barbuti E, Rinaldi V, Tufano L, Pozzilli V, Ianniello A, Marinelli F, De Luca G, Prosperini L, Tomassini V and Pozzilli C (2021) Case Report: Multiple Sclerosis Relapses After Vaccination Against SARS-CoV2: A Series of Clinical Cases. *Front. Neurol.* 12:765954. doi: 10.3389/fneur.2021.765954

